

WHAT DRIVES UNIVERSITY STUDENTS' ENTREPRENEURIAL INTENTION? EVIDENCE FROM EAST JAVA INDONESIA

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Abstract

Entrepreneurship plays a vital role in improving a country's economy. However, public interest in entrepreneurship in many developing countries remains low, especially among the younger generation. The paper examines the drivers of entrepreneurial intention among college students. The primary data was collected from a survey with 273 students in Malang Regency. Using structural equation modelling, the results show that 1) entrepreneurship education has a positive and significant effect on entrepreneurial orientation and intention, 2) entrepreneurial orientation can lead to an intention in entrepreneurship, and 3) entrepreneurial orientation is an intervening variable in the effect of entrepreneurship education on entrepreneurial intention. The interaction between peer influence as a moderating variable and entrepreneurship education indicates that the former can strengthen the latter in instilling entrepreneurship intention. Finally, corporate social responsibility can amplify the influence of entrepreneurial education on intention in entrepreneurship. The research finding is applicable not only in Indonesia but also in other developing countries with low levels of entrepreneurship.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship education, entrepreneurial orientation, social influence, corporate social responsibility, entrepreneurial intention

1. INTRODUCTION

Indonesia entered Asia Pacific's free trade in 2020. Entrepreneurs must answer the arising challenges and opportunities and increase national economic growth. The entrepreneurial sector can absorb 97 per cent of the total workforce (Setiawan, 2010). Its development can increase GDP by 60 percent, boost exports, and spur innovations (Siregar et al., 2021). The Indonesian government continues to support entrepreneurial growth through various programs. The Ministry of Cooperatives and Small and Medium Enterprises (KUKM) provides capital support through collaboration with banks and cooperatives (Rochimawati, 2016).

However, the efforts to increase the number of entrepreneurs in Indonesia have not been fruitful. Based on the data released by the Global Entrepreneurship Index Rank of All Countries, Indonesia's level is low and ranked 75th, below other ASEAN countries (Zoltan et al., 2019). The latest BPS data shows that educated unemployment due to the pandemic among diploma graduates increased by 8.5 per cent and among undergraduates by 25 per cent. This should serve as a momentum for evaluation and strategy development to improve the graduates' soft skills and fulfil the demand in the job market.

The main problem is the ingrained mindset in the society. Most people would prefer to find employment than start their own business. At the university level, the graduates' choices have always been between looking for a job or becoming an entrepreneur (Totoh, 2020). Being an

entrepreneur is considered hard. Also, certain professions are considered a symbol of success (Muhammad, 2019). Additionally, low entrepreneurial capacity, rigid regulations, and limited access to capital also hinder the sector's development. Besides, the Indonesian education system does not teach entrepreneurship from a young age and tends to produce a labour mentality rather than an entrepreneur mentality. Producing entrepreneurs requires the integration of an entrepreneurial element into the education system, starting from elementary school to the higher education curriculums (Muhammad, 2019).

Universities need to work together with other stakeholders to reduce unemployment. For example, although the government has issued a relevant regulation, there is a gap between the graduates' skills and the demands in the job market. Regulation of the National Accreditation Board for Higher Education Number 5 of 2019 concerning Study Program Accreditation Instruments necessitates the types of work the graduates are expected to obtain (Totoh, 2020).

Entrepreneurial intention is manifested in entrepreneurial behaviours, which are reflected in entrepreneurial attitudes and motivation to start a business. Subjective norms in the family, among close friends, and community are a strong environmental drive for individuals to start a business. An individual's ability to form entrepreneurial behaviour is also related to behavioural control (Indrayanti & Iskandar, 2020). Entrepreneurial skills and knowledge can be obtained from a higher education institution. The programs are usually carried out systematically, consistently, and directedly. Joining these programs will help build students' orientation and train them to think creatively like an entrepreneur. The orientation can spark entrepreneurial intentions and intention (Chrismardani, 2016), so when students graduate, their options are not limited to finding a job only but also to creating jobs.

However, an important point to note is that students' intentions can be galvanised or crushed during the process of learning and going in and out of the entrepreneurial business. A social environment can encourage entrepreneurship, so building a strong community is essential. Students are easily influenced by their social groups; especially their peers (Patricia & Silangen, 2016). They can also be a source of information and exchange ideas. Therefore, peer influence is an essential driver of the entrepreneurial venture (Patricia & Silangen, 2016; Nurhaidah, 2018). Universities can capitalise on this peer influence by, for example, creating a collaborative environment.

This research focuses the variables on entrepreneurship education, entrepreneurial orientation, and peer influence. Past research has shown that entrepreneurship education influences entrepreneurial orientation (Devi, 2017) and intention to start a business (Patricia & Silangen, 2016; Suarjana & Wahyuni, 2017; Ndofiropi, 2020; and Liu et al., 2019). However, Mwatsika and Sankhulani (2016) found the opposite. Therefore, further research is needed to corroborate the findings. Regarding the effect of entrepreneurial orientation on intention in entrepreneurship, research has shown that the two factors are positively correlated (Devi, 2017; Buana et al., 2017). However, Koe (2016) argued that not all dimensions of entrepreneurial orientation influence entrepreneurial intention (the impact is insignificant).

As for peer influence, Patricia and Silangen (2016) argue that there is a relationship between peer social influence and entrepreneurial intention. However, they did not thoroughly discuss the role of peer influence as a moderating variable of the influence of education on entrepreneurial orientation. In fact, no prior research has explored this. Therefore, the current research aims to fill this gap. As for corporate social responsibility (CSR), despite its important role in corporate culture, no studies have examined its role as a variable moderating the influence of education on entrepreneurship intention. Martinez and Monteagudo (2020) have shown that CSR impacts social entrepreneurship, but the study does not directly discuss the role of CSR as a moderating variable of the effect of entrepreneurship education on entrepreneurial orientation. This is another gap that the current research aims to fill.

Then, on the influence of entrepreneurial orientation on intention in entrepreneurship, research studies by Devi (2017) and Buana et al. (2017) support this opinion, but Koe's research (2016) provides a contradictory opinion. From some of the studies that have been mentioned, the evidence only points out the direct influence of the dependent and independent variables.

Referring to the past studies above, it could be concluded that 1) there are different findings regarding variables that strengthen or weaken the influence of entrepreneurial education on entrepreneurial intention; 2) there are differences in the perspective of the variables used; 3) there has not been a study examining peer influence and CSR as moderating variables in the influence of entrepreneurship education on entrepreneurial intention.

Therefore, the current study aims to analyse: a) the effect of entrepreneurial education on entrepreneurial orientation; b) the effect of entrepreneurial education on entrepreneurial intention; c) the effect of entrepreneurial orientation on entrepreneurship; d) the role of entrepreneurial orientation as an intervening variable in the effect of entrepreneurial education on entrepreneurial intention; e) the role of peer influence as a moderating variable in the effect of entrepreneurial education on entrepreneurial intention; f) the role of CSR as a moderating variable in the influence of entrepreneurial education on entrepreneurial intention.

2. RESEARCH FRAMEWORKS

2.1 The effect of entrepreneurial education on entrepreneurial orientation

The primary purpose of entrepreneurship education is to change students' views, behaviour and intentions so that they understand entrepreneurship, instil an entrepreneurial mindset and equip students with the necessary skills and competence. Entrepreneurial learning must be able to transfer knowledge and skills and create a real business and entrepreneurial spirit (Keatet al., 2011).

Entrepreneurship education can shape students' mindset, attitudes, behaviour, and orientation to become true entrepreneurs so that it directs them to choose entrepreneurship as a career choice (Wibowo & Pramudana, 2016). At its core, entrepreneurship education should influence entrepreneurial orientation (Devi, 2017). However, Mwatsika and Sankhulani (2016) argue that entrepreneurship education cannot influence all the orientation dimensions. The first research hypothesis is formulated as follows:

H1: Entrepreneurial education has an effect on entrepreneurial orientation

2.2. The influence of entrepreneurial education on entrepreneurial intention

Entrepreneurial education can increase students' self-efficacy through the access to knowledge and skills needed to start a business, which will ultimately affect students' intention in entrepreneurship (Chandra & Budiono, 2019). Suarjana and Wahyuni (2017) state that entrepreneurship education has an influence on students' intention to start a business. This is in line with the research conducted by Ndofiropi (2020) and Liu et al. (2019). The second research hypothesis is formulated as follows:

H2: Entrepreneurial education has an effect on entrepreneurial intention

2.3. The influence of entrepreneurial orientation on entrepreneurial intention

Orientation is an important construct in entrepreneurship (Bolton & Lane, 2012). Entrepreneurial orientation is an important predictor in determining the performance and growth of a company (Tang et al., 2008). Understanding individual entrepreneurial orientation is needed to design an intervention (Bolton & Lane, 2012). Stronger entrepreneurial orientation among students can have a significant impact on entrepreneurial intention. The third research hypothesis is formulated as follows:

H3: Entrepreneurial orientation has an effect on entrepreneurial intention

2.4. Entrepreneurial orientation as an intervening variable in the effect of entrepreneurial education on entrepreneurial intention

Entrepreneurial education through curriculums and programs is likely to foster a person's entrepreneurial orientation. The orientation can be measured through the ability to innovate and be creative, show a proactive attitude toward business opportunities, be aggressive in competition, take risks and be independent to start a new business (Devi, 2017). Purwanto and Trihudyatmanto (2018) stated that students seldom take risks, especially in terms of the use of funding and capital. They tend to spend money consumptively instead. The fourth research hypothesis is formulated as follows:

H4: Entrepreneurial orientation can act as an intervening variable in the influence of entrepreneurial education on entrepreneurial intention.

2.5. The role of peer influence as a moderating variable in the effect of entrepreneurial education on entrepreneurial intention

Peers with the same interests in the entrepreneurial world can influence each other (Patricia & Silangen, 2016; Nurhaidah, 2018). The fifth research hypothesis is formulated as follows:

H5: Peer influence can strengthen the influence of entrepreneurial education on entrepreneurial intention.

2.6. Corporate social responsibility as a moderating variable in the influence of entrepreneurial education on entrepreneurial intention

Corporate social responsibility (CSR) has now reached out to higher education institutions to instil entrepreneurial spirit among university students. CSR plays a vital role in shaping a company's image (Muttaqin, 2010). Many local corporations have now taken various steps in directing programs for university students. One step is making universities partners for research and apprenticeship activities (Muttaqin, 2010). The sixth research hypothesis is formulated as follows:

H6: Corporate social responsibility can strengthen the influence of entrepreneurial education on entrepreneurial intention

The indicators and statement items in the questionnaire were adapted from previous research or developed by the researchers themselves. For more details, the variables, indicators, items, and reference sources are summarised in Table 1

Table 1: Variables, Indicators, Items, and Reference Sources

Variable	Indicator	Item	Measurement	Reference
Entrepreneurial education (X)	Creative Ideas (X ₁)	X _{1.1}	First Order	Theory: Gerba (2012); Paco et al. (2013); Buana et al. (2017) Empirical: Handayati et al. (2020)
		X _{1.2}		
	Knowledge (X ₂)	X _{2.1}	First Order	
		X _{2.2}		
	Skills and Competence (X ₃)	X _{3.1}	First Order	
		X _{3.2}		
	Opportunities for Business (X ₄)	X _{4.1}	First Order	
X _{4.2}				
Entrepreneurial orientation (Z ₁)	Innovativeness (Z _{1.1})	Z _{1.1.1}	First Order	Theory: Bolton & Lane (2012); Empirical: Keh et al. (2007)
		Z _{1.1.2}		
	Proactiveness (Z _{1.2})	Z _{1.2.1}	First Order	
		Z _{1.2.2}		
	Risk-Taking (Z _{1.3})	Z _{1.3.1}	First Order	
		Z _{1.3.2}		
Peer influence (Z ₂)	Interested in a peer's business idea (Z _{2.1})	Z _{2.1.1}	First Order	Theory: Hurlock (2011) Empirical: Patricia & Silangen (2016)
		Z _{2.1.2}		
	Peer business motivation (Z _{2.2})	Z _{2.2.1}	First Order	
		Z _{2.2.2}		
	Peer collaboration (Z _{2.3})	Z _{2.3.1}	First Order	
		Z _{2.3.2}		
Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) (Z ₃)	Contribution to society (Z _{3.1})	Z _{3.1.1}	First Order	Theory: Sabatini & Sudana (2019); Hadyarti & Mahsin (2019); Caesari et al. (2015) Empirical: Martinez & Monteagudo (2020); Jalilvand, et al. (2017)
		Z _{3.1.3}		
	Charitable activities (Z _{3.2})	Z _{3.2.1}	First Order	
		Z _{3.2.3}		
	Not only profit-oriented (X _{3.3})	Z _{3.3.1}	First Order	
		Z _{3.3.2}		
Entrepreneurial intention (Y)	Attitudes (Y ₁)	Y _{1.1}	First Order	Theory: Ajzen (1991); dan Ajzen & Naim (2016) Empirical: Angola et al. (2019)

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Data

This research was conducted at state universities in Malang, namely Universitas Brawijaya, Malang State University, and Malang State Islamic University. Research locations are selected based on the Malang City Government data. Since 2017, the government has been fostering entrepreneurship among its young generation.

The sampling technique is a purposive sampling technique based on specific selection criteria: 1) having completed the entrepreneurship module; (2) having participated in the PKM-Entrepreneurship program; (3) being undergraduate students of the year 2019. The total population was obtained from the student organisations from Universitas Brawijaya, State University of Malang, and Malang State Islamic University. Calculated using the Solving formula, the total sample was 273.

The data was collected from a survey. The questionnaire aimed to measure the attitudes and orientation of respondents in a large population (Babbie, 2017). The questionnaire as the research instrument was sent directly to the respondents. It was a closed questionnaire with a Likert scale ranging from one (strongly disagree) to five (strongly agree).

3.2. Data analysis

The data analysis in this study uses inferential statistics. The analysis aims to prove the hypothesis, with the results generalisable for the entire population. The inferential technique uses structural equation modelling (SEM)—a multivariate statistical technique combining a factor analysis and a regression analysis. SEM examines the relationships between variables in a model, between indicators and their constructs or between constructs (Babbie& Austin, 2000). In this study, data processing and analysis were carried out using Microsoft Excel, SPSS, and AMOS.

4. RESEARCH RESULTS

4.1 Respondents' Characteristics

Figure 1 shows the respondents' characteristics. Seventy-seven respondents (28.21%) were students of management; 66 respondents (24.18%) came from the accounting department; 44 people (16.12%) came from the development economics department; 27 respondents (9.89%) came from the economics, finance, and banking majors; 25 respondents (9.16%) came from the Islamic economics, and 20 respondents (7.33%) came from the entrepreneurship department. Figure 1 shows the characteristics by major, and Figure 2 shows the characteristics by gender. Most respondents (157 people or 57.51%) were male, and the rest were female (116 people or 42.49%).

Figure 1: Characteristics by Major

Figure 2: Characteristics by Gender

4.2. Validity and Reliability Test Results

A validity test checks the indicators' accuracy level. Are liability test measures the internal consistency of the indicators in a construct? Because the indicators are multidimensional, the validity of each variable was tested by looking at the factor loading of the relationship between the observed variable and the latent variable. The reliability was tested using Cronbach Alpha. The results of data processing are as follows.

Tabel 2: confirmatory factor analysis

Construct	Indicatif	Factor Loading	Coefficientt Cronbach's Alpha
Entrepreneurial education (X)	X1	0,930	0,903
	X2	0,911	
	X3	0,881	
	X4	0,890	
	X5	0,905	
	X6	0,894	
	X7	0,877	
	X8	0,902	
Entrepreneurial orientation (Z ₁)	Z11	0,603	0,804
	Z12	0,578	
	Z13	0,752	
	Z14	0,736	
	Z15	0,679	
	Z16	0,601	
Social Influence of Classmate (Z ₂)	Z21	0,917	0,820
	Z22	0,883	
	Z23	0,850	
	Z24	0,883	
	Z25	0,881	
	Z26	0,882	
Corporate Social Responsibility (Z ₃)	Z31	0,915	0,861
	Z32	0,899	
	Z33	0,875	
	Z34	0,898	
	Z35	0,900	
	Z36	0,883	
	Z37	0,867	
Entrepreneurial intention (Y)	Y1	0,727	0,796
	Y2	0,729	
	Y3	0,775	
	Y4	0,818	
	Y5	0,809	
	Y6	0,679	

The confirmatory factor analysis shows that the factor loadings of each question indicator that makes up each variable are mostly 0.5. Therefore, the instrument indicators for each construct can be considered valid. Meanwhile, the internal consistency reliability test results for each variable show good results. The Cronbach's Alpha coefficient was 0.7, which meets the standard requirement (Hair et al., 1998).

5.1. Model Testing

In the SEM model, the measurement model and the structural model are estimated simultaneously. This method could meet the standard of the fit model. The highest probability derives from the interaction between the measurement model and the structural model

estimated using the one-step approach to SEM, which is used when the model is grounded in a strong theory and the data validity and reliability are excellent. The estimation results and the SEM model using AMOS 22.0 are shown in the Goodness of Fit Figure and Table below.

Figure 3: One-Step Approach Model

Table 3: Evaluation of Criteria for Goodness of Fit

Criteria	Result	Critical value	Note
Cmin/DF	3,571	$\leq 2,00$	Not Fit
Sig.	0,000	$\geq 0,05$	Not Fit
RMSEA	0,097	$\leq 0,08$	Not Fit
GFI	0,732	$\geq 0,90$	Moderate
AGFI	0,692	$\geq 0,90$	Not Fit
TLI	0,790	$\geq 0,95$	Moderate
CFI	0,807	$\geq 0,94$	Moderate

In evaluating the one-step approach model, not all the goodness of fit criteria shows good model evaluation results, which means that the model is not following the data. This means that the conceptual model developed based on the theory has not been supported by facts. Therefore, the following modifications need to be made.

Figure 4: One-Step Approach Modified Model

Table 4: Evaluation of Criteria for Goodness of Fit

Criteria	Result	Critical value	Note
Cmin/DF	1,907	≤ 2,00	Fit
Probability	0,000	≥ 0,05	Not Fit
RMSEA	0,08	≤ 0,08	Fit
GFI	0,977	≥ 0,90	Fit
AGFI	0,928	≥ 0,90	Fit
TLI	0,944	≥ 0,94	Fit
CFI	0,962	≥ 0,94	Fit

The evaluation shows that all goodness of fit criteria showed a fairly good result, meaning that the model is now following the data. The conceptual model developed based on the theory has been fully supported by facts. In other words, this model is the best model to explain the relationship between variables in this study.

5.2. Hypothesis Testing and Causal Relationships

The determinant of the sample covariance matrix was $8877105.859 > 0$, which indicates no multi collinearity or singularity in this data. In other words, the assumptions are met. The magnitude of the regression coefficient of each factor can be trusted, as shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Causality Test Results

Regression Weights			Ustd Estimate	Std Estimate	Prob.
Fakcor	⇒	Factor			
Entrepreneurial education (X)	⇒	Niat Berwirausaha (Y)	0,243	0,297	0,000
Entrepreneurial education (X)	⇒	Entrepreneurial orientation (Y)	0,285	0,512	0,000
Entrepreneurial orientation (Z ₁)	⇒	Entrepreneurial intention (Y)	0,175	0,119	0,004
Int_SIOCM (SIOCM* PK) (Int1)	⇒	Entrepreneurial intention (Y)	0,001	0,003	0,005
Int_CSR (CSR* PK) (Int2)	⇒	Job Satisfaction (Y)	0,002	0,007	0,000
Sig.					≤ 0,05

From the probability level of the causal relationship direction, the hypotheses are as follows:

1. Entrepreneurial Education variable (X) has an effect on Entrepreneurial Intention (Y), acceptable (causal probability 0.000 0.05 (significant))
2. Entrepreneurship Education Variable (X₂) has an effect on Entrepreneurial Orientation Variable (Z₁), acceptable (causal probability 0.000 0.05 (significant))
3. Entrepreneurial Orientation Variable (Z₁) has an effect on Entrepreneurial Intention Variable (Y), acceptable (causal probability 0.004 0.05 (significant))
4. Variable Int_SIOCM (SIOCM*PK) (Int1) has an effect on Entrepreneurial Intention Variable (Y), acceptable (causal probability 0.005 0.05 (significant))
5. Variable Int_CSR (CSR*PK) (Int2) has an effect on Entrepreneurial Intention Variable (Y), acceptable (causal probability 0.000 0.05 (significant))

5.3. Verification of entrepreneurial orientation variable as an intervening variable

An intervening variable theoretically affects the relationship between the independent and dependent variables in an indirect relationship. In this study, the intervening variable is the entrepreneurial orientation variable. The testing is done through the Sobel test calculator, with the results as follows.

Figure 5: Sobel Test Calculator Diagram

Figure 5 show that entrepreneurial orientation is proven an intervening variable in the effect of entrepreneurship education on entrepreneurial intentions. The one-tailed probability value was $0.000 < 0.05$.

6. DISCUSSION

6.1. The effect of entrepreneurial education on entrepreneurial orientation

The results show that entrepreneurship education has a positive and significant effect on entrepreneurial orientation, as indicated by a probability value of 0.000, which is smaller than the specified limit of 0.05. A positive influence means that entrepreneurship education has a unidirectional influence. The better the entrepreneurship is taught, the stronger the entrepreneurial orientation formed. The purpose of entrepreneurial education is to change students' views, behaviours, and intentions to build an entrepreneurial mindset. Entrepreneurial learning transfers not only knowledge and skills but also creative thinking and problem-solving skills (Keat et al., 2011) so that entrepreneurship can become a career choice (Wibowo & Pramudana, 2016). The finding in this research supports previous research by Devi (2017), stating that entrepreneurship education fosters entrepreneurial orientation.

6.2. The influence of entrepreneurial education on entrepreneurial intention

The results show that entrepreneurship education positively and significantly affects entrepreneurial intention. This is indicated by a probability value of 0.000, which is smaller than the specified limit of 0.05. Entrepreneurial education has a unidirectional influence, which means that the better the entrepreneurial education, the higher the entrepreneurial intention. Education has an important role in the development of entrepreneurship to support sustainable growth. Entrepreneurship education can increase students' self-efficacy and intention to start a business (Chandra & Budiono, 2019; Suarjana & Wahyuni, 2017; Ndofiropi, 2020; Liu et al., 2019).

6.3. The Influence of entrepreneurial orientation on entrepreneurial intention

The results show that entrepreneurial orientation positively and significantly affects entrepreneurial intention. This is indicated by a probability value of 0.004, which is smaller than the specified limit of 0.05. A positive influence means that entrepreneurial orientation has a unidirectional influence. The stronger the entrepreneurial orientation, the more the entrepreneurial intention grows.

6.4. The role of entrepreneurial orientation as an intervening variable in the effect of entrepreneurship education on entrepreneurial intention

The results show that entrepreneurial orientation is an intervening variable in the effect of entrepreneurship education on entrepreneurial intentions, shown in the one-tailed probability value of $0.000 < 0.05$. Entrepreneurial orientation can be measured through the ability to innovate and be creative, a proactive attitude toward business opportunities, competitiveness, and the ability to take risks and independently start a new business (Devi, 2017).

6.5. The role of peer influence as moderating variable in the effect of entrepreneurial education on entrepreneurial intention

The results show that the peer influence variable has a probability value of 0.003, which is smaller than the specified limit of 0.05 and is marked with a positive coefficient. In other words, peer influence can strengthen the impact of entrepreneurial education on entrepreneurial intention. This finding implies that the government must continue fostering cooperation and improving the entrepreneurial ecosystem. The young generation now is capable of building networks and attaining good academic achievement (Abdila, 2020) because most universities in Indonesia focus on producing graduates who are ready to join the labour market. Educational curricula, student activities, and learning practices are geared toward meeting the industry's needs.

However, higher education institutions should be able to build students' characters and mind sets so that the graduates will be ready for both the industry and entrepreneurial ventures (Devi, 2017), which can minimise the unemployment rate through the emergence of entrepreneurial activities and Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs). Additionally, higher education institutions should collaborate with the industries and the government to create an ecosystem that supports entrepreneurship.

6.6. The role of corporate social responsibility (CSR) as a moderating variable in the influence of entrepreneurial education on entrepreneurial intention

The results also show that the interaction of CSR as a moderating variable has a probability value of 0.007, which is smaller than the specified limit of 0.05 and is marked with a positive coefficient. This shows that CSR can strengthen the influence of entrepreneurial education on entrepreneurial intention. The implication is that stakeholders need to incorporate CSR concepts and practices into the curricula. For example, the lessons from the COVID-19 pandemic can be generalised and taught in classrooms and during an internship or company visits.

To illustrate, unemployment is not only the responsibility of the government but also of companies. They need to think of how they can survive, for example, amid a pandemic or during a financial crisis in the new normal era (Nurfitriani, 2020). The company can optimise CSR programs and funding to build resilience and strengthen the company's internal business sustainability. Companies need to formulate strategic CSR initiatives by considering the impact of COVID-19 on society and business activities. The CSR funds can be allocated to reduce the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on internal conditions. For example, the programs can involve employees and consumers to sustain the business in the new normal era (Nurfitriani, 2020).

7. CONCLUSION

This study aims to analyse 1) the effect of entrepreneurial education on entrepreneurial orientation. b) the effect of entrepreneurial education on entrepreneurial intention; c) the effect of entrepreneurial orientation on entrepreneurial intention; d) the role of entrepreneurial

orientation as an intervening variable in the effect of entrepreneurial education on entrepreneurial intention; e) examine and analyse the role peer influence as a moderating variable in the effect of entrepreneurial education on entrepreneurial intention; f) the role of corporate social responsibility as a moderating variable in the influence of entrepreneurial education on entrepreneurial intention.

This study uses primary data collected by surveying 273 students in Malang Regency. Using structural equation modelling, the results show a positive and significant correlation among the abovementioned variables. The findings suggest that the Indonesian education system needs to highlight entrepreneurial education. Further, this implication could be applied not only in Indonesia but also in other developing countries with low levels of entrepreneurship.

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